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Table 2. Settling response of WBPH females on rice varieties at 24, 48, 72, and 96 h after release.

Variety	Individuals settled on a hill (no.)				Eggs/hill (no.)
	24 h	48 h	72 h	96 h	
IR2035-117-3	2 a	1 a	1 a	2 a	152 a
BR46	5 ab	2 b	2 a	1 a	103 a
Ba Khleu	7 bc	8 c	5 bc	6 b	521 d
Rong Lem	8 bc	8 c	6 bc	4 b	572 d
Xoai cat	8 bc	8 c	5 bc	4 b	325 b
Base	8 bc	7 c	5 bc	4 b	410 c
La	10 c	8 c	4 b	6 b	267 b
Keo Cha A	15 c	13 d	14 d	13 c	804 d
TN1	19 c	30 e	37 e	43 d	2,974 e
CV (%)	29	10	27.6	21.6	6

that about 30% were moderately resistant to WBPH. Among these, seven varieties were tested for the nonpreference mechanism.

Two days after infestation (DAI), a significantly higher population of nymphs was found on susceptible Taichung Native 1 (TN1) than on the

other varieties. TN1 wilted 5 DAI. Insect settling response was significantly lower on Base, BR46, Xoai cat, and the resistant varieties than on the other varieties (Table 1).

Settling response of WBPH females and number of eggs laid/hill were lowest on BR46 (Table 2). Egg density varied significantly across the varieties and was positively correlated with the density of females settled on a hill.

The nonpreference mechanism due to pubescence and hardness of plant tissue makes local rice varieties unsuitable hosts for WBPH settling, feeding, and egg laying. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Influence of low night temperatures on rice spikelet differentiation in high-altitude swamps in Burundi

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Rice was only recently introduced in high-altitude swamps in Burundi. Several factors account for reduced yield, one of which is spikelet sterility. We conducted an experiment to determine the origin of sterility and the stage at which the plant is most sensitive to low night temperatures.

Plants grown from seedling stage to harvest in cylindrical plastic posts were used. Soil was taken from a fallow bean field. We compared varieties Yunnan 3, Tokombana, Kirundo 9, Facagro 71, and Facagro 57 at two sites at different altitudes: Bujumbura, located on Tanganyika plain at 800 m altitude with a warm, humid climate and temperature not below 15 °C; and Kizunga swamp, at 1900 m altitude on the Zire-Nile ridge, with a cold climate and night temperature often below 10 °C, which results in poor rice-growing conditions.

Five pots containing three plants each were prepared per variety for each of two treatments. In the first, plants were grown in Bujumbura from seedling to harvest. In the second, plants were grown in

1. Distribution of spikelet types in five varieties of rice grown in Bujumbura, Burundi.

2. Effect of 20 d at Kizunga during panicle initiation on the distribution of spikelet types.

Bujumbura, transferred to Kizunga at panicle initiation for 20 d, and then returned to Bujumbura.

The second treatment caused very strong spikelet sterility in five varieties. Some sterile spikelets were poorly differentiated, characterized by small size and discolored glumes. Well-differentiated sterile spikelets stayed green until harvest. Different spikelet types were counted on 10 healthy panicles randomly selected (two per pot) per variety for each treatment (Figs. 1 and 2).

More than 70% of the spikelets were fertile in all varieties and the rate of poorly differentiated sterile spikelets was very low with the first treatment. In contrast, 20 d at Kizunga between panicle initiation and the end of microsporogenesis stage considerably increased the frequency of poorly differentiated sterile spikelets, especially in Facagro 71, Facagro 57, and Tokombana.

Glumes and floral organs of poorly differentiated sterile spikelets were observed under a binocular microscope. Three types of morphological abnormalities due to low night temperatures were detected: presence of a supernumerary envelope around the floral organs between two glumes, presence of two or more fused ovaries, and reduced number or size of stamens.

Sterility rises when rice is grown at high altitude with low night temperatures. When there is cold stress during panicle initiation and spikelet differentiation, morphological malformations of spikelets and flowers contribute to sterility. ■